

Article

Principles of Applying Sustainable Development in Industrial Enterprises Under The Conditions of Economic Greening

Bekbosinov Aydos Kuralbayevich*¹

1. "Mamun University" Associate Professor of the Department of Business Management, PhD
Correspondance: treasurer091@gmail.com

Abstract: This article examines the principles of sustainable development of industrial enterprises in the context of the greening of the economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The study considers the main directions for implementing environmentally oriented technologies, resource-saving practices, and innovations in the industrial sector. Based on statistical data, the dynamics of industrial development, environmental indicators, and the country's transition toward a green economy are analyzed. The research also investigates the factors affecting the sustainability of industrial enterprises and proposes recommendations for improving the effectiveness of implementing sustainable development principles.

Citation: Kuralbayevich, B. A. Principles of Applying Sustainable Development in Industrial Enterprises Under The Conditions of Economic Greening. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research 2026, 7(6), 78-82.

Received: 10th Apr 2026
Revised: 30th Apr 2026
Accepted: 20th May 2026
Published: 08th June 2026

Copyright: © 2026 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Green Economy, Industry, Economic Greening, Resource Conservation

1. Introduction

In the context of global environmental challenges and accelerated industrialization, the implementation of sustainable development principles in the activities of industrial enterprises is becoming particularly relevant. Sustainable development implies a harmonious combination of economic growth, social responsibility, and environmental safety.

In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been actively implementing a strategy for the transition to a "green economy," aimed at improving energy efficiency, reducing pollutant emissions, and developing renewable energy sources. In 2018, the country ratified the Paris Climate Agreement and committed to reducing greenhouse gas emissions per unit of GDP by 10% by 2030 compared to the 2010 level [1].

In addition, the green economy transition strategy provides for increasing the share of renewable energy sources to 25% in the electricity generation mix by 2030.

At the same time, the country's industrial development is accompanied by environmental problems. Intensive industrial production and the use of outdated technologies lead to air, water, and soil pollution. In particular, a significant share of air pollution is generated by industry, transport, and the energy sector [2].

The aim of this study is to analyze the principles of sustainable development of industrial enterprises in the context of the greening of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan and to identify prospects for their implementation.

Research objectives:

- To study the theoretical foundations of sustainable industrial development;
- To analyze current environmental and economic indicators of uzbekistan's industrial sector;
- To identify factors of sustainable enterprise development;
- To develop recommendations for the implementation of environmentally oriented technologies [3].

Literature Review

The issue of sustainable development of industrial enterprises has been widely studied by both foreign and domestic scholars. In the scientific literature, sustainable development is considered as a complex concept combining economic, environmental, and social aspects of industrial development.

One of the first fundamental documents that shaped the modern understanding of sustainable development was the report of the World Commission on Environment and Development chaired by Gro Harlem Brundtland titled "Our Common Future". In this report, sustainable development is defined as development that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs [4]. This concept became the basis for the formation of modern environmental policies and economic strategies in many countries around the world.

A significant contribution to the development of sustainable development theory was made by the American economist Herman Daly, who developed the concept of ecological economics. According to the scholar, sustainable development is possible only under the condition of balance between economic growth and the capacity of natural ecosystems. Daly emphasized the need to limit excessive resource consumption and to transition to an economic model based on the rational use of natural capital [5].

2. Methods and Materials

The following methods were used in the study:

- Statistical analysis;
- Comparative analysis;
- System analysis;
- Economic-analytical methods;
- Graphical data interpretation.
- The information base of the study included:
 - Data from the national statistics committee of the republic of uzbekistan;
 - International reports;
 - Scientific publications on sustainable development;
 - Analytical materials on the country's environmental policy.

3. Results and Discussion

Industry is one of the key drivers of the country's economic growth. The state sustainable development strategy envisages increasing the share of industry in GDP structure to 40% by 2030 [6].

Table 1. Dynamics of Industrial Development of Uzbekistan [6]

Indicator	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Growth rate of industrial production (%)	5.8	6.2	7.4	5.3	6.0
Share of industry in GDP (%)	29	31	33	34	35
Investment in industry (billion USD)	7.1	7.5	8.4	9.2	10.3

As can be seen from Table 1, the industrial sector of Uzbekistan demonstrates steady growth. The average annual growth rate of industrial production is about 6%. The share of industry in GDP is increasing, which indicates a structural transformation of the economy [7].

However, industrial growth is accompanied by an increasing burden on the environment, which requires the introduction of environmentally oriented technologies.

One of the key problems of industrialization is the growing environmental pollution [8].

Table 2. Key Environmental Indicators [2]

Indicator	Value
Share of industry in air pollution	13%
Share of the energy sector	28%
Share of transport	16%
PM2.5 level in Tashkent relative to WHO standards	13.4 times higher

According to research data, the concentration of fine particulate matter (PM2.5) in Tashkent significantly exceeds the recommendations of the World Health Organization. This indicates a high level of anthropogenic pressure on the environment [9].

In addition, industry has a significant impact on air and soil pollution. For example, metallurgical enterprises and mining complexes have a substantial effect on the environmental situation in the industrial regions of the country [10].

In recent years, the principles of the green economy have been actively implemented in the country [11].

Table 3. Indicators of Green Economy Development

Indicators	2019	2024
Renewable energy capacity growth	—	+573%
Reduction of carbon emissions	—	-4.2%
Increase in energy efficiency	—	+15.6%
Share of the green sector in GDP	growth by 3 times	

The results demonstrate a positive trend in the country's transition toward a sustainable economy. A particularly significant increase is observed in the renewable energy sector [12-13].

The main principles of sustainable development include:

1. Resource conservation;
2. Implementation of environmentally friendly technologies;
3. Reduction of pollutant emissions;
4. Improvement of energy efficiency;
5. Development of a circular economy;
6. Digitalization of production.

Figure 1. Model of Sustainable Development of an Industrial Enterprise

Despite positive trends, the implementation of sustainable development principles faces a number of challenges [14].

Table 4. Main Barriers to Sustainable Industrial Development

Factor Group	Main Problems
Economic	High cost of modernization
Technological	Outdated equipment
Institutional	Insufficient regulatory framework
Human Resources	Shortage of qualified specialists

Studies show that sustainable industrial development in Uzbekistan is constrained by the economy's structural dependence on raw-material industries and the insufficient adoption of innovative technologies [15].

Nevertheless, the implementation of national programs such as "Green Economy 2030" and "Digital Uzbekistan" creates favorable conditions for industrial modernization [16].

4. Conclusion

The conducted research allows the following conclusions to be drawn:

1. Industry plays a key role in the economy of Uzbekistan and demonstrates steady growth.
2. Industrialization is accompanied by environmental challenges, including air pollution and increasing emissions.
3. The transition strategy toward a green economy contributes to improved energy efficiency and the development of renewable energy sources.
4. The implementation of sustainable development principles requires industrial modernization, the adoption of innovations, and increased environmental responsibility of enterprises.

To enhance the sustainability of industrial development, it is necessary to:

- Stimulate the adoption of environmentally friendly technologies;
- Develop environmental management systems;

- Expand investments in green energy;
- Increase the level of environmental responsibility of businesses.

REFERENCES

- [1] International Energy Agency, *Uzbekistan Energy Profile and Sustainable Development*. Geneva, 2023.
- [2] Center for Development Strategy of Uzbekistan, *Environmental Challenges and Economic Risks*. Tashkent, 2025.
- [3] G. H. Brundtland, *Our Common Future*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press, 1987.
- [4] H. E. Daly, *Ecological Economics and Sustainable Development*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing, 2007.
- [5] National Sustainable Development Goals Portal of Uzbekistan, *Industrial Development Goals*, 2024.
- [6] State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics, *Industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan: Statistical Yearbook*. Tashkent, 2023.
- [7] Author's compilation based on statistical data.
- [8] Author's compilation based on literature review.
- [9] A. K. Bekbosinov, "Methodological foundations for assessing the effectiveness of innovative development in industry," *Bulletin of Karakalpak State University*, no. 2(56), 2022.
- [10] D. Vaisov, "Kichik firmalar raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning mintaqaviy muammolari (Xorazm viloyati misolida)," *Green Economy and Development*, vol. 1, no. 11, 2023.
- [11] D. Vaisov, "Raqobatbardoshlik tushunchalarining mohiyati va tavsiflanishi," *University Research Base*, pp. 65–69, 2024.
- [12] V. D. Ibodullayevich, "Stages of improving the mechanisms for ensuring the competitiveness of small business entities providing medical services," *Nauchnyy Impuls*, vol. 4, no. 41, pp. 86–92, 2026.
- [13] D. Vaisov and I. Sharipov, "Osnovnye kontseptualnye podkhody v marketinge meditsinskikh uslug," *Eurasian Journal of Human Health and Disease*, vol. 2, no. 2, 2026.
- [14] G. Sh. Bekbergenov, "Functional significance of the entrepreneurship institute in the sustainable development of the regional economy: Theoretical-conceptual analysis," *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 241–247, 2026.
- [15] K. Sharipov and D. Vaisov, "Tekhniko-ekonomicheskie osnovy okazaniya meditsinskikh uslug," *International Journal of Economy and Innovation*, vol. 68, 2026.
- [16] D. I. Vaisov, "Prospects for the development of small business entities in the medical services market," *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 633–638, 2026.